

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: The social necessity of life required the development of scientifically based methods of managing the educational process, accepting the theoretical and methodological aspects of educational management as a special scientific direction. It is necessary to justify the main aspects of educational management from the point of view of theory and research and experience in order to arm leaders with special knowledge and skills. This will help them to correctly solve the specific problems that arise in the management process, to objectively solve educational puzzles.

Key words: need for new personnel (sociologist, psychologist, programmer, etc.) for the management system;

In this regard, one cannot ignore the fact that there is almost no transfer of experiences related to education management, a serious drawback of education. Because the main problem today is to fundamentally change the quality of the management system. For this, simplification of the management system, unification of its related structures, reduction of unnecessary links in between, and rational use of the essence of tasks at the level of each system are the most important tasks.

The following are the specific features of the scientific management of the educational system:

- the dialectic unity of state and social educational interests reflected in the content of management;
- the expansion of management aspects related to the complex tasks facing the modern school;
- to bring the development of the system to a new, qualitatively more perfect state by perceiving and using and studying the laws of educational management;
- continuous improvement of forms and methods of education management based on national characteristics;

introduction of mathematical, statistical and economic methods of management using modern electronic computers and development of management techniques.

Currently, there are different approaches to defining the management process. Management is interpreted as a process of making management decisions and implementing it, or as an educational process, in other words, as a direct or echo result of the continuous movement of information in the management process.

Management is a process that directly affects the activity of each employee, group or organization under certain conditions, and is aimed at achieving the highest and best results possible.

Another, relatively correct direction of the management process is systematic management, because it is only clear; can be managed through the system. In fact, most of the interpretation of the term "management" is through a systems approach to management.

Although the concept of "system" is often encountered in pedagogical practice, in fact, we cannot always immediately perceive the essence and place of the system. The system is the unity of purpose, content, principles, tasks, form, method and way of management, which affects objective learning and perception and its improvement. The educational management system is an open system due to its connection with the external environment. The task of this system is directly subordinated to the goal of education, training and development. Since the management process actually takes place among all the complex systems, it is the basis for looking at it as a whole system. It has the following features:

- the presence of certain parts with their own characteristics;
- interrelationship and interdependence of parts (having a common unity);
- having internal organization;
- bending and bending of parts, elements;
- exist in a certain external environment, form a single unit and, in turn, be the basis for continuing the system's activity;
- goal-oriented activity, striving to achieve the goal;

dynamic movement, development;

- ability to maintain a steady state;
- existence of contradiction in nature;
- active and timely participation of the pedagogical team in management work.

The education management system is a direct activity based on individual management and personal responsibility. So, education management is a socio-economic and organizational-pedagogical process, which works using various methods and tools to increase the efficiency of all educational work and achieve high results.

It can be stated with full confidence that without knowing the laws of objective reality, one cannot systematically approach management, one of the most important of which is the law of integrity (integrity) of school management. The unity of the socio-economic system is the most necessary feature of this law.

The unity of the socio-economic system determines the unity of the public education system. As a mechanism that supports this integrity, the management system has a special place and is expressed in the following aspects:

- educational management is implemented based on the interest of the community, which in turn leads to a single, multi-level management;
- subordination and subordination in various elements of management work are determined by the fact that they are aimed at one goal;
- temporary errors in some elements of the control system do not prevent its functioning as a whole;
- there is a complex chain of relationships within the management system. It is a communicative relationship that exists from the highest level to the lowest level, and this chain is inseparable from each other;
- despite the fact that the forms of management are diverse, the relations at all levels of the management apparatus are stable;
- the mechanism of education management operates at all levels of management in various district relations. These are financial-economic, organizational-pedagogical, organizational-technical, social-psychological relationships, all of which serve a single purpose;
- the more common ownership requires a unified management system, the more the unified management system supports common ownership and existing production relations;
- all objective laws of society and production development determine and apply the characteristics of the management system.

The unity of the education management system, clear unity as legality, generalization and consistency, equal distribution and functioning of education in one standard, which in turn applies to all public education systems.

Dependence of laws of centralization and decentralization. Centralization is the main feature of management in all stages of human activity. The centralized management system of public education has the composition of such a management system and there are strong connections that are permanent in all its parts. These relationships define the subordinator and subordinator, Centralized management implies the coordination of management decisions at all levels. On the other hand, it is a mistake to say that purposive management imposes strict regulation on all systems of public education. Each of its steams has its own conditions of operation.

Therefore, management should assume certain independence in solving specific problems. This is done by decentralizing. This is especially true for the education system. In it, the creative nature of all members of the team is subject to the internal legality of the school management system. Relinquishment of centralized management gives each branch, system and sub-systems the right to independent activity.

The regularity of relations between the manager and the managed system is visible in various aspects of the content of management, because it depends on political, economic, organizational and social factors. These systems are related to each other both quantitatively and qualitatively, regardless of which joints they are in. Currently, the quantitative ratio of the controlling and controlled system is changing in favor of the latter. This process is a direct reflection of the existing law. The more the public basis of education management develops, the less need there is for a higher management system body.

Economic aspects are also an important factor in the interaction between the controlling and controlled systems. Changes in these systems are defined by an increase or decrease in their value. This law also has an objective economic basis.

The increase in the value of the managed system is due to the following reasons:

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